

ADVANCES IN THE SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY OF CARBON NANOTUBE COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

This paper reviews recent advancements in the science and technology of carbon nanotubes and their composites. The presentation examines the hierarchical structural levels of carbon nanotube reinforcements that have been developed for composite materials with particular emphasis on multifunctional performance.

Keywords: Carbon Nanotubes, Nanocomposites, Multi-Functionality

INTRODUCTION

In recent years there has been tremendous research advances made in the scientific base for carbon nanotubes, and this has enabled significant improvements in the technology of carbon nanotube-based composites. The interplay between basic science and engineering has resulted in some of the most exciting accomplishments in the development of multifunctional materials. This paper highlights these accomplishments based on the hierarchical structural levels of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) used in composites. Both single walled (SWCNTs) and multi-walled (MWCNTs) carbon nanotubes have been utilized. These structural levels, ranging from 1-D to 2-D to 3-D, are highlighted below.

- (1) Surface modification of SWCNTs
- (2) Electrospinning of CNT polymer fibers
- (3) CNT-modified surfaces of advanced fibers
- (4) CNT-modified interlaminar surfaces
- (5) Highly oriented CNTs in planar form
- (6) Dispersed CNT networks
- (7) Textile assemblies of CNTs

SURFACE MODIFICATION OF SWCNTs

Optimization of the properties of SWCNT composites is primarily dependent on several factors, namely purity of the SWCNTs [1], homogeneity of the dispersion of the (debundled) SWCNTs in the host matrix [2, 3], nature and concentration of the functional groups [4], nature of the interfacial bonding between SWCNTs and the host matrix [5, 6], aspect ratio (length/diameter) and nanotube loading.

Both theoretical and experimental studies have recognized that optimization of the polymer-carbon nanotube interface is critical for the translation of the exceptional properties of carbon nanotubes to advanced composites. The construction of chemical bonds between the nanotubes and polymer matrix offers the most efficient solution for the formation of strong interface [5]. This can be accomplished by chemical modification of the carbon nanotubes so that functional groups attached to the nanotubes can efficiently cross-link with the polymer matrix. Systematic engineering of the functional groups in the carbon nanotubes leads to significant improvement of the composite properties. Examples include the synthesis of SWCNT-nylon composites with greatly improved Young's modulus, tensile strength and thermal stability [4-6], PAMAM-functionalized SWCNT/epoxy composites [7]. It is very important that the functionalized CNTs have good dispersibility in solvents and/or polymers because an efficient interface can be achieved only with debundled nanotubes.

ELECTROSPINNING OF CNT/POLYMER FIBERS

Electrospinning is an electrostatic induced self-assembly process, which has been developed for decades, and a variety of polymeric materials have been electrospun into ultra-fine filaments [8]. Electrospinning of CNT/polymer fibrils is motivated by the idea to align the CNTs in a polymer matrix and produce CNT/polymer nanocomposites in a continuous manner. The alignment of CNTs enhances the axial mechanical and physical properties of the filaments.

Ko and co-workers have adopted the co-electrospinning technique for processing CNT/PAN (polyacrylonitrile) and GNP (graphite nanoplatelet)/PAN fibrils. Following Ko *et al.* [8-10], the concept of electrospinning process can be explained using Figure 1. Here, a high voltage is applied between an oppositely charged polymer fluid and a metallic collection screen. The fluid is contained in a glass syringe which has a capillary tip (spinneret). When the voltage reaches a critical value, the electric field overcomes the surface tension of the suspended polymer and a jet of ultra-fine fibers is produced. As the solvent evaporates, a mesh of nano to micro size fibers is accumulated on the collection screen. The fiber diameter and mesh thickness can be controlled through the variation of the electric field strength, polymer solution concentration and the duration of electrospinning. In the processing of CNT/PAN nanocomposite fibrils, polyacrylonitrile with purified high-pressure CO disproportionation (HiPCO) SWCNTs dispersed in dimethylformamide, which is an efficient solvent for SWCNTs, are co-electrospun into fibrils and yarns. Aligned fiber collection can be made through suitable arrangement of parallel electrodes. Figure 2 shows the ESEM (field emission environmental electron scanning microscope) images of electrospun nanofibers with 1 wt. % of SWCNTs in aligned and random form of deposition.

Figure 1. Schematic setup of the electrospinning of random and aligned fiber assemblies [8].

Figure 2. ESEM images of electrospun nanofibers. (a-c) aligned 1 wt. % SWCNT/PAN fibers at various magnifications; and (d) random 1 wt. % SWCNT/PAN fibers [8].

It has been demonstrated that up to 10 wt. % SWCNT reinforced PAN fibrils can be electrospun in a diameter range of 50-400nm by controlling the SWCNT/PAN concentration in the solution [8]. The efficiency of transferring the properties of CNTs to the micro- and macro-structural levels relies very much on the dispersion of CNTs in the polymer, interfacial bonding between CNTs and the matrix, orientation of SWCNTs in the fibril direction as well as the alignment of fibrils in the yarn assembly.

CNT-MODIFIED SURFACES OF ADVANCED FIBERS

Carbon nanotubes were grown directly on carbon fibers using chemical vapor deposition (Figure 3). When embedded in a polymer matrix, the change in length scale of carbon nanotubes relative to carbon fibers results in a multiscale composite, where individual carbon fibers are surrounded by a sheath of nanocomposite reinforcement. Single-fiber composites have been fabricated to examine the influence of local nanotube reinforcement on load transfer at the fiber/matrix interface. Results of the single-fiber composite tests indicate that the nanocomposite reinforcement improves interfacial load transfer (Figure 4). Selective reinforcement by nanotubes at the fiber/matrix interface likely results in local stiffening of the polymer matrix near the fiber/matrix interface, thus, improving load transfer [11].

Figure 3: SEM micrographs of carbon fibers (a) before and (b) after surface modification with carbon nanotubes [11].

Figure 4: Birefringence patterns of single fiber fragmentation [11].

CNT-MODIFIED INTERLAMINAR SURFACES

Many attempts have been made by researchers in recent years in modifying the interlaminar surface by CNTs for improved mechanical and transport properties. The

recent approach by Garcia *et al.* [12] and Blanco *et al.* [13] is particularly interesting in that they successfully integrated aligned CNTs with existing carbon fiber prepreg materials and processing. This is accomplished by first growing a vertically aligned CNT forest at high temperature. The CNTs are then transferred using a rolling transfer scheme to prepregs at room temperature, taking advantage of the tack of the prepregs. The aligned CNT forest can readily draw up the polymer through capillary action when laminated and forms a bond with the polymer matrix.

According to Garcia *et al.* [12] the ideal aligned CNT reinforcement would be comprised of short forest (<20 μm). The CNTs penetrate each ply by $\sim 10\ \mu\text{m}$. Therefore an $\sim 20\ \mu\text{m}$ forest would introduce no additional thickness to the ply interlayer, which is commonly known to be detrimental to in-plan properties. Figure 5a shows the “transfer-printing” process where the prepreg is attached to a cylinder that is rolled across the Si substrate containing the CNT forest. Figure 5b shows the fully transferred CNT forest on a carbon fiber/epoxy prepreg. The CNT forest maintains vertical alignment and is neither broken nor buckled (Figures 5c and 5d). The addition of a second ply of prepreg then creates 2-ply laminate with an aligned CNT interlayer. Two aerospace-grade unidirectional prepregs were reported in Ref. [12] for processing 24-layer laminates with a CNT interlayer in Mode I and Mode II fracture tests. In their initial testing, the CNT-modified interface is observed to increase fracture toughness 1.5~2.5X in Mode I and 3X in Mode II. Evidence of CNT bridging was observed in fracture micrographs. Figure 6 gives an illustration of the ideal hybrid interlaminar architecture showing the aligned CNTs placed in between the two plies of a laminated composite.

Figure 5. Transfer-printing of vertically-aligned CNTs to prepreg: (a) Illustration of the ‘transfer-printing’ process; (b) CNT forest fully transplanted from its original silicon substrate to the surface of a Gr/Ep prepreg ply; (c and d) SEM images of the CNT forest, showing CNT alignment after transplantation [12].

Figure 6. Illustration of the ideal hybrid interlaminar architecture: (a) CNTs placed in between two plies of a laminated composite; and (b) close-up of the crack, showing CNTs bridging the crack between the two plies. Illustrations are not to scale [12].

HIGHLY ORIENTED CNTs IN PLANAR FORM

The development of paper-like CNT film, also known as buckypaper, has attracted much attention in the past decade because of its potential applications in catalysis, filtration, sensors, actuators, supercapacitors, artificial muscles, hydrogen storage materials and anode materials in lithium ion batteries. Most of the processing approaches for buckypapers have utilized the procedures of dispersion and filtration of a suspension of CNTs. To maximize the translation of individual nanotube mechanical and physical properties to the macroscopic film level, it is attractive to align the CNTs with high volume content. Here, the classical technique of alignment under a high magnetic field and the more recent technique of “domino pushing” are reviewed.

The work of Refs. [14, 15], for instance, reported the electrical, thermal and mechanical properties of magnetically aligned buckypapers, which were produced by filtrating SWCNT suspensions in a 17.3T magnetic field. For thermal conductivity measurements, the buckypapers were also impregnated with an epoxy matrix material. In the nanocomposites, the SWCNT volume loading is about 50% for aligned composites and 25-30% for random composites. Experimental results show that in the pristine aligned buckypaper mats, the thermal conductivity is relatively high (42W/mK). The ratio of axial to transverse direction thermal conductivity is ~3.5. When the aligned buckypaper is infiltrated with an epoxy matrix, the thermal conductivity drops significantly, by nearly an order of magnitude, and becomes comparable to that of the non-aligned (random) composite. It should be noted that molecular dynamic simulations reveal that the thermal conductivity of individual SWCNT could be as high as 6,600W/mK and experimental values for both SWCNTs and MWCNTs are as high as 3,000 W/mK at room temperature.

In the electrical resistivity experiments of Ref. [15], the buckypapers were infiltrated with polycarbonate solution for processing the nanocomposite film with CNT concentrations in the 40-60 wt% range. The average bulk resistivity of the neat buckypaper is ~0.0049 Ω cm while the values of the composites are 1.7 to 3 times higher than that of the neat buckypaper. The potential applications of the conductive

composites may include lightweight coating materials for electromagnetic interference shielding, lightning strike protection of various structures and electrostatic discharging in electronic components.

The magnetic alignment method is limited in that the high magnetic field makes the broad application of this method inconvenient and the problems of nanotube waviness and agglomeration are not easily resolved. For producing buckypapers with long and straight CNTs and at the same time minimizing the above mentioned difficulties, Wang *et al.* [16] developed a simple and effective macroscopic manipulation of aligned CNT arrays termed “domino pushing”. This is a “dry” and *in situ* method for the preparation of aligned buckypapers with large areas. This method is shown schematically in Figure 7. The method comprises three steps. First, the MWCNTs, grown by CVD on a substrate with a round area of 10cm in diameter and $\sim 100\mu\text{m}$ in thickness, are covered with a piece of microporous membrane and all the CNTs in the array are forced down in one direction by pushing a cylinder with constant pressure. All CNTs in the array are attracted together due to strong van der Waals force and form an aligned buckypaper. Second, the aligned buckypaper is then peeled off from the silicon substrate with the membrane. Finally, ethanol is applied to the membrane and allowed to permeate through and enables the aligned buckypaper to be peeled-off from the membrane. The resulting aligned buckypaper has a density about 20 times larger than that of the CNT array. The thermal conductivities of the buckypaper studied in Ref. [16] are 153 W/mK and 72 W/mK, respectively, in the axial and transverse directions. Obviously, the measured conductivity value will increase when the buckypaper is pressed thinner with a higher stress. The specific density of the manually pressed buckypapers in Ref. [16] is about 0.6 g/cm^3 , only about half of the ideal value of 1.34 g/cm^3 . The measured axial electrical conductivity of the buckypaper is 20,000 S/m at room temperature, while the value for buckypapers with randomly oriented CNTs is 15,000 S/m.

Figure 7. Schematics of the domino pushing method: (a) Forming aligned buckypaper, (b) peeling the buckypaper off from the silicon substrate, (c) peeling the buckypaper off from the microporous membrane [16].

The above experimental results led Wang *et al.* [16] to conclude that, unlike the conventional buckypapers, in which the CNTs are often wavy and agglomerated, the “domino pushing” gives rise to the morphology of fairly straight CNTs. The significant improvements in thermal and electrical performance offer better potential of buckypapers for multifunctional applications.

DISPERSED CNT NETWORKS

The use of advanced fiber composites continues to expand in many structural applications. These composites are susceptible to the formation of micro-scale damage, such as interfacial debonding, matrix cracking, fiber breakage and delamination. The initiation of micro-scale damage has significant implications on the durability and performance of fiber composites. With the more frequent utilization of advanced fiber composites in primary structural applications there is a fundamental challenge to enhance reliability and performance while reducing maintenance. As a result there is broad scientific and technical interest in the development of techniques capable of monitoring the health of composite structures.

Developments in the production of nanostructured materials and composites with novel material properties have created opportunities where unique functionality can be added to existing material systems. Owing to their unique mechanical and physical properties measured at the nanoscale, the development of carbon nanotube-based composites has seen tremendous research activity over the past decade [17, 18]. As compared to traditional fibrous reinforcement, where the diameters are on the micron scale, carbon nanotubes are three orders of magnitude smaller. Due to their extremely small size, it is possible for carbon nanotubes to penetrate the matrix-rich regions of the composite around the fibers and between the plies of the composite. The formation of an electrically conductive network of nanotubes in the polymer matrix surrounding the fibers enables the nanotubes to be a distributed sensing network that can be utilized for sensing of deformation and damage *in situ*. As cracks propagate in the composite the conducting pathways are broken in the percolating network. The capability to sense damage is unique to nanostructured materials since a nano-scale conductor is necessary to sense the formation of a micro-sized crack [19, 20].

Figure 8: Optical micrograph (left) showing transverse microcracking in a cross-ply laminate and (right) graph showing the influence of transverse crack density on the damaged resistance and elastic modulus [21].

The graph in Figure 8 shows the crack density as measured by edge replication during cyclic loading and the damaged resistance, as defined in Ref. [20]. There is an overall linear relationship between the formation of transverse cracks and the increase in the damaged resistance per specimen length ($\Delta R/L$), showing that damaged resistance may be utilized as a quantitative measure of overall damage. The 90° degree ply becomes saturated with cracks near a crack density of 16 cm⁻¹. Even though the 90° ply is saturated with cracks there is a very small degradation in the elastic modulus of the laminate.

TEXTILE ASSEMBLIES OF CNTs

Bogdanovich and co-workers [22-24] have pioneered research in textile assemblies of CNTs. They have demonstrated the feasibility in processing of nanotube yarns with high twist spun from nanotube forests, plied nanotube yarn processed from a number of single nanotube yarns with counter-direction twist and 3-D nanotube braids fabricated from 36 five-ply yarns. In addition, the plied nanotube yarns and 3-D braids were used as through-the-thickness (Z) yarns in 3-D weaving process.

The challenges in making nanotube fibers/yarns with desirable properties, according to Bogdanovich *et al.* [24], are in achieving the maximum possible alignment of the nanotubes or their bundles within the yarn, increasing the nanotube packing density within the yarn and enhancing the internal bonding among the nanotubes. The fabrication of CNT yarns was made possible due to the discovery of Jiang *et al.* [25] that CNTs can be self-assembled into yarns up to 30cm long, simply by being drawn out of a forest of aligned CNTs. Zhang *et al.* [26] modified the drawing process by adding a twist during nanotube drawing. Bogdanovich and co-workers then produced MWCNT single-ply yarns and 5-ply yarns, which were made by over-twisting five single yarns and subsequently allowing them to relax until reaching a torque-balanced state. Figure 9 is an SEM image of a 5-ply MWCNT yarn.

It is interesting to note that a plied nanotube yarn has several levels of hierarchical structures. First, the CVD synthesized MWCNTs are 300 μm long and 10 nm in diameter and they formed about 20 nm diameter bundles in a nanotube forest. Simultaneous draw and twist of the bundles produced $\sim 10 \mu\text{m}$ diameter single yarn.

Figure 9. SEM image of 5-ply MWNT yarn [24].

Figure 10. SEM image of the first nanotube 3-D braid [24].

Besides single-ply and 5-ply yarns, Bogdanovich and co-workers have also demonstrated the fabrication of other multi-ply yarns which have been used in 3-D braiding process as well as Z-yarns in 3-D weaving processes. Figure 10 is an SEM image of a braided CNT yarn using 36 ends of 5-ply nanotube yarns. It is currently possible to produce tens of meters of continuous MWCNT yarns. It is reported that no visible damage to the nanotube yarns is imparted by the braiding process and the 3-D braids are very fine, extremely flexible, hold sufficient load, and are well suited for the use in any other textile formation process, or directly as reinforcement for composites. The reported elastic and strength properties of carbon nanotube composites so far are rather low in comparison with conventional continuous carbon fiber composites. It is believed that the properties can be substantially improved if the processing methods and structures are optimized [24].

CONCLUDING REMARKS

In the field of composite materials scientists and engineers have been tailoring materials at the microstructural level for decades. The recent advances in both the production and characterization of nanostructured materials have enabled the expansion of composite reinforcement levels to the nanometer scales. Through fundamental understanding of their processing-structure-performance relations the creation of multifunctional composites with controlled hierarchical structures may offer a wide range of future applications.

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